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Chemistry of Euphorbiaceae. Part-III†.
Isolation of Lupane Group of Triterpenes
from *Givotia rottleriformis* Griff.

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GIVOTIA *rottleriformis* Griff. (N.O. *Euphorbiaceae*) is a moderate-sized tree found in the Deccan forests. The wood is used locally for making painted toys¹. Literature survey has shown that this plant has not been examined for its crystalline principles. The bark has been examined in the present investigation.

The ether-extract of the bark furnished a brownish yellow solid (3%). It was fractionated into acidic (2.5%) and neutral (0.5%) fractions with 10% NaOH solution.

The acidic fraction was homogeneous on tlc and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 298-300°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +5^\circ$; δ 4.7 (2H, isopropylidene); m/z 446 ($C_{30}H_{48}O_8$). It was identified as betulinic acid by comparison of the compound, methyl ester (CH_3N_3 , m.p. 220-22°) and acetate (Py-Ac₂O, m.p. 290-95°) with authentic sample of betulinic acid, methyl betulinatate and acetyl betulinic acid².

The neutral fraction is not homogeneous on tlc and showed two spots. It was adsorbed on a column of silica gel (< 200 mesh) and eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1, 2 dm³) and benzene (2 dm³)

successively. The petroleum ether-benzene eluate furnished lupeol (0.05%), m.p. 210-12°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +24^\circ$; δ 4.75 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

The benzene eluate furnished betulin (0.35%), m.p. 250-52°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +19^\circ$; δ 4.70 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

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Chemical Components of *Rhamnus virgata*

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EARLIER investigation¹ on *Rhamnus virgata* (Syn. *R. dahuricus*) of Rhamnaceae family has shown the presence of rhamnocitrin and rhamnazin. Since no extensive work has been carried out on *R. virgata*, we undertook its chemical examination for studying the phenolic components.

Stems (3 kg) of *R. virgata* from Solan, Himachal Pradesh (India) were extracted with hot ethanol and the extractives were chromatographed over silica gel. Elutions with petroleum ether to ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 4) afforded eight compounds. Of these, five have been characterised as chrysophanol, physcion, rhamnocitrin, kaempferol and 3-*o*-methylquercetin on the basis of spectral properties and direct comparisons. The remaining three are rare metabolites and have been labelled as A, B and C.

Compound A: It crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene, m.p. 186-188°. Its acetate was prepared from Ac₂O-Py and crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 140-42°; δ (CDCl₃) 6.72 (1H, br s

† Part-II, 24-Nor-cyclolaudenol from *Euphorbia nivulata*, *Phytochemistry* communicated.

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